

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

**AN OVERVIEW COMPREHENSIVE PROSPECT OF HERBAL
FORMULATION IN INDIA****Miss. Jarripothu Prashanthi¹, Mr. V. S. Chandrasekaran^{2*}, Dr. K. Venugopal³**¹Final year B Pharmacy, Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati – 517 506.²Associate Professor, Department of Pharmaceutical Biotechnology, Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati – 517 506.³Professor and Principal, Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati – 517 506.**Abstract:**

In India, there is a growing demand for herbal medicines and other herbal healthcare products (in both developing and emerging nations of the world healthcare sector). World Health Organization (WHO) defines herbal medicines as plant-containing active ingredients converted as finished and labelled medicinal Products. India has the largest supply of medicinal herbs, with around 8,000 herbal treatments organized in the Ministry of AYUSH systems. The Drugs and Cosmetics Act of 1940 established standards for medications and the relevant Pharmacopoeias' which set the requirements for individual monographs of each active constituent. The herbal formulation needs vigorous authentication and quality evaluation of active ingredients including their organoleptic, microscopic, and chemical assessments. The pharmaceutical industry has shown less attention to herbal formulation due to the complex drug development process, like quality control, marketing values, and administrative guidelines. The Critical step in developing herbal formulations is approving and ensuring the safety and efficacy of herbal products in the medicinal world. By understanding these demands the manufacturers, and regulators work together to ensure that herbal Products are highly qualified with safety & efficacy for desirable therapeutic effects.

Keywords: *Herbal, Formulations, Quality Control, Pharmacopeia, Regulatory Authority.*

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Please cite this article in press Jarripothu Prashanthi et al., An Overview Comprehensive Prospect Of Herbal Formulation In India., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2024; 11 (10)

1. INTRODUCTION:

The World Organization (WHO) describes herbal medicines as "aerial or underground plant parts or other plant material that contain an active ingredient as finished, labelled medicinal product. According to data from the WHO, 80 percent of the population currently uses herbal medicines for some part of basic healthcare. The largest supplier of medicinal herbs in India. India's forests are home to a variety of aromatic and medicinal plants that are used to make medicines. In India's AYUSH systems, some 8,000 herbal treatments have been organized. The Drugs and Cosmetics Act of 1940 establishes standards for medications, and the relevant Pharmacopoeias also set down requirements for individual monographs. The release of the 52 drugs standard Herbal Pharmacopoeias represents a step in the right direction. For licensing any herbal product within the two categories of ASU medications and Patent proprietary medicines, the first schedule of the D and C Act lists the allowed texts that must be followed. In recent decades, evidence has been available on herbal therapy's therapeutic effects and clinical efficacy. Still, the new thrust area is investigating the synergy of composite herbal formulation and their interaction with chemical drugs (1,2).

According to reports, around 8000 herbal species are utilized as ethnomedicine, and ethnic communities have devised 25000 formulations that must be identified, verified, and documented. The pharmaceutical industry has shown less attention to developing herbal medicines due to the complex process of drug development, quality control, security, adequacy, promotion, and administrative guidelines, and medical people are also not interested much in it. For low-income and developing countries, this scenario becomes a financial burden. In this review, we have highlighted the prospects and problems related to plant-derived drug development and its commercialization, as well as the future breadth of research possibilities.

2. METHODOLOGY OF HERBAL FORMULATIONS:

Herbal formulation is a dosage form consisting of one or more herbs or processed herbs in particular quantities to provide specific nutritional, and cosmetic benefits and are meant to diagnose, treat, and alleviate disease of human beings or animals, and alter the structure of human beings or animals. The herbal formulation contains an herbal substance or in combination with one or more herbal substances to process like extraction, distillation fractionation,

fermentation include power. Generally, the plant (or) plant part we take as raw material in the process preparation of herbal formulation should be qualified so that the process of extraction of the active ingredients from the plant part can be done efficiently with the quality and purity aspects. As Quality control plays an important role in herbal formulations WHO has given certain guidelines (3,4,5)

Guidelines for assessment for Herbal drug formulations:

WHO (World Health Organisation) has given certain guidelines for assessment of herbal drugs and most of the countries have adopted those guidelines. The following are the aims and objectives of WHO guidelines in standardizing herbal drugs.

- * Quality control of crude drug material, plant preparations, and finished products.
- * Stability assessment and shelf life
- * Safety assessment; documentation of safety based on experience or toxicological studies
- * Assessment of efficacy by studying the pharmacology of drugs and evaluating their biological activity.

3. STANDARDISATION & QUALITY EVALUATION OF HERBAL DRUGS

3.1. AUTHENTICATION OF HERBAL DRUGS

There exist plenty of species and subspecies of plants in the world so it is difficult to identify them Properly, hence it is essential that before starting any processes on herbs, they need to be properly identified and authenticated by a reputed institution or organization. The following institutes are involved in the authentication of herbs (6,7).

Name of the Institutes

- Central Council for Research in Ayurveda and Siddha (CCRAS), Janakpuri, New Delhi, Delhi.
- Central Council for Research in Unani medicine (CCRUM), Jamia Nagar, Okhla, New Delhi, Delhi.
- Central Council for Research in Homeopathy (CCRH), Janakpuri Institutional Area, Janakpuri, New Delhi, Delhi
- Central Council for Research in Yoga and Naturopathy (CCRYN), Institutional Area, Sewa Marg, Pocket D 1A, Janakpuri, New Delhi, Delhi
- Central Council for Research in Indian Medicine (CCIM), New Delhi, Delhi
- Central Council for Homeopathy, Janakpuri New Delhi, Delhi

Laboratories

- Pharmacopoeial Laboratory for Indian Medicine (PLIM) located at Central Govt. Enclave, Kamla Nehru Nagar, Ghaziabad, Uttar Pradesh.
- Homeopathy Pharmacopoeia Laboratory (HPL), Kamla Nehru Nagar, Ghaziabad, Uttar Pradesh.
- National Institute of Homeopathy (NIM), Bidhannagar, Kolkata, West Bengal.
- National Institute of Ayurveda (NIA), Jaipur, Rajasthan.
- National Institute of Unani Medicine (NIUM), Bengaluru, Karnataka.
- National Institute of Naturopathy (NIN), Pune, Maharashtra.
- National Institute of Siddha (NIS), Chennai, Tamilnadu.
- Institute of Post- Graduate Training and Research in Ayurveda (IPGTRA), Jamnagar, Gujarat
- Rashtriya Ayurveda Vidyapeeth (RAV), New Delhi.
- Morarji Desai National Institute of Yoga (MDNIY), New Delhi.

3.2.ORGANOLEPTIC/MACROSCOPIC EVALUATION

Organoleptic properties refer to the ones that can be observed by the senses of the personnel that describe color, odor, taste, consistency, fractured surface of barks, shape, texture, and appearance of drugs evaluated Visual inspection provides the simplest and quickest means by which to establish identity, purity, and quality (12,13).

3.3. MICROSCOPIC EVALUATION**(a) Qualitative microscopy**

It is used to identify the herbal drug by studying its microscopic characteristics such as transverse section, longitudinal section, powder microscopy, leaf constants, trichomes, and stomata. Leaf constants include the determination of palisade ratio, stomatal number, stomatal index, vein islet number, and vein islet index.

(1) Stomatal number/index:

The stomatal number is the average number of stomatal cells present per square millimeter of the epidermis. The stomatal index is the percentage number of stomata formed by the total number of epidermal cells including the stomata being counted as one cell.

(2) Palisade ratio:

It is the average number of palisade cells beneath each upper epidermal cell

(3) Vein islet number:

It is the number of vein islets per square millimeter area of leaf calculated from the central part of the lamina between the midrib and the margin

(b)Quantitative microscopy:

It is used to evaluate the quantity/amount of the substance present. Example Lycopodium spore method to determine the number of starch grains, length, several fibers, and trichomes present.

3.4. PHYSICAL EVALUATION**Determination of foreign organic matter**

Drugs should be free from molds insects, animals, fecal matter, and other contamination such as earth stones and extraneous matters. Foreign organic matter should be not more than 2% w/w.

Determination of ash value

The residue remaining after incineration is the ash content of drugs, which simply represents inorganic salts, naturally occurring in drugs or adhering to it due to adulteration. Three types of ash values are determined.

- Total ash

Total ash is designed to measure the number of inorganic impurities present in the crude drug. The drug material is subjected to incineration at a temperature of about 500 to 600°C to remove all the carbons. Total ash usually consists of carbonates, phosphates, silicates, and silica

- Acid insoluble ash

Acid-insoluble ash is the residue obtained after extracting the total ash with HCl. It gives an idea about the earthy matter present in the drug.

- Water soluble ash

The total ash content which is soluble in water is known as water-soluble ash. It gives an idea about the presence of water-soluble salts present in the drug.

Determination of extractive value

It gives an idea about the number of chemical constituents present in the drug. Extractive values are again sub-classified based on the nature of constituents present in the drug as water-soluble extractive, alcohol-soluble extractive, volatile ether soluble extractive, and non-volatile ether soluble extractive value.

Determination of moisture content

10gm of the drug is taken in an evaporating dish. Then it is dried at 105 °C for 3 hours and weighed again. Drying and weighing are continued for an hour interval until the difference between two successive weighing corresponding to not more than 0.25 percent. Then reading is taken after a constant weight is reached and the moisture content is determined.

Refractive index

When a ray passes from one medium to another of different densities, it is bent from its original path. Thus, the ratio of the velocity of light in a vacuum to its velocity in a substance is termed as refractive index of the second medium. Depending upon purity, it is constant for a liquid and can be considered as one of its standardizations.

3.5. CHEMICAL EVALUATION

It consists of qualitative and quantitative methods (14,15)

Qualitative chemical evaluation

Qualitative tests comprise various chemical tests to identify the nature of compounds present in crude drugs. Examples:

- Test for alkaloids: Mayer's test, Dragendroff's test, Hager's test, Wagner's test, etc.
- Test for glycosides and sugars. Borntrager's test, Molisch's test, Bal jet test, Legal test, Ke Killiani test, etc
- Tests for phytosterols: Liebermann's and Burchard's tests.
- Tests for tannins and phenols: Ferric chloride test
- Tests for proteins and amino acids: Millen's test, Biuret's test, Ninhydrin test.
- Tests for gums and mucilage: Swelling index.

Quantitative chemical evaluation

Quantitative tests include chemical assays and chromatographic methods which are used to quantify the chemical compounds present in the crude drug.

3.6. CHROMATOGRAPHIC TECHNIQUES

The chromatographic techniques are the new and most common methods (Figure 1) used to separate identify and quantify the plant constituents. It consists of various methods which follow.

Figure 1: Chromatographic Techniques – Various types

Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC)

TLC technique has become a most important tool for separation and determination of natural products. It is a simple, economical, and rapid method to analyze plant extracts and carry out the fingerprinting of samples by using the standard or marker compounds.

High-Performance Thin Layer Chromatography (HPTLC)

It is one of the very useful methods for the qualitative and quantitative analysis of plant extracts. It is the advanced form of TLC with a shorter time and precise results.

High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC)

It is one of the most versatile, safest, dependable, fastest, and sensitive chromatographic techniques for the quality control of drugs. The term liquid chromatography refers to those methods where separation takes place in a packed column which acts as stationary phase. A mobile phase is used as an eluent. In HPLC, the mobile phase is forced through the column under high pressure.

Gas Liquid Chromatography (GLC)

GLC is the most selective and versatile form of gas chromatography commonly it is used for assay and analysis of starting materials and drug substances, qualification of drug substances in formulations, and assay of impurities and solvents in the drug substances.

Column Chromatography

Basically, it is a liquid chromatography in which the mobile phase in the form of liquid passes over the stationary phase packed in a column. The column is made of either glass or metal. It is the oldest and most commonly practiced method for the isolation of pure compounds.

3.7. BIOLOGICAL EVALUATION

It consists of the following evaluation methods

(a) Bitterness test

Medicinal plant materials that have a strong bitter taste ("bitters") are employed therapeutically, mostly as appetizing agents. Their bitterness results in an increase of secretions of the gastrointestinal tract, especially of gastric juice.

- The bitter property of the plant material is determined by comparing the threshold bitter concentration of an extract of the plant materials with that of a dilute solution of quinine hydrochloride.

- The bitterness value is expressed in units equivalent to the bitterness of a solution containing 1 gm of quinine hydrochloride in 2000 ml water.

- Bitterness value can be calculated in the units per g using the following formula:

$$2000 \times c/a \times b$$

Where

a = the concentration of the stock test solution (ST) (mg/ml)

b = the volume of test solution ST (in ml) in the tube with the threshold bitter concentration,

c = the volume of quinine hydrochloride R (in mg) in the tube with the threshold bitter concentration.

Bitterness value is evaluated by tasting the drug and comparing it with the standard drug.

(b) Haemolytic value

Many medicinal plant materials of the families Caryophyllaceae, Araliaceae, Sapindaceae, Primulaceae, and Dioscoreaceae contain saponins.

- The most characteristic property of saponins is their ability to cause hemolysis: when added to a suspension of blood, saponins produce changes in erythrocyte membranes, causing hemoglobin to diffuse into the surrounding medium.
- The hemolytic activity of the plant material, or preparation containing saponins, is determined by comparison with that of a reference material, saponin R, which has a hemolytic activity of 1000 units per gram.
- The hemolytic activity of the medicinal plant is calculated using the formula:

$$1000 \times a/b$$

Where,

1000 = the defined hemolytic activity of saponin R in relation to ox blood,

a = quantity of saponin R that produces total hemolysis (g)

b = quantity of plant material that produces total hemolysis (g)

(c) Swelling index

- The swelling index is the volume in ml taken up by the swelling of 1g of plant material under specific conditions.
- Its determination is based on the addition of water or a swelling agent as specified in the test procedure for each individual plant material (either whole, cut, or pulverized)

(d)Foaming index

- Many medicinal plant materials contain saponins that can cause a persistent foam when an aqueous decoction is shaken.
- The foaming ability of an aqueous decoction of plant materials and their extracts is measured in terms of a foaming index.
- Foaming index can be calculated by using the formula:
Foaming index=1000/a

Where: a=the volume of the decoction used for preparing the dilution in the tube where foaming to a height of 1cm is observed.

(e)Determination of pesticide residues

WHO and FAO (Food and Agricultural Organization) set limits on pesticides, which are usually present in herbs. These pesticides are mixed with the herbs during the cultivation.

- Pesticides like DDT(Dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane), BHC (Benzene hexachloride), toxaphene, and aldrin cause serious side effects in human beings if the crude drugs are mixed with these agents.
- The average pesticidal residue should not exceed more than 1%.
- The average pesticidal residual limit (ARL) in mg of pesticide per kg of plant material can be calculated on the basis of the maximum acceptable daily intake of the pesticide for humans (ADD), as, recommended by WHO, and the mean daily Intake (MDI) of the medicinal plant material.

60/MEDI x 100.

Where:

ADI = maximum acceptable daily intake of pesticide (mg/kg of body weight);

E= extraction factor, which determines the transition rate of the pesticide from the plant material into the dosage form.

MDI = mean daily intake of medicinal plant products.

(f) Determination of arsenic and other heavy metals

- Contamination of medicinal plant materials with arsenic and heavy metals can be attributed to many cases including environmental pollution and traces of pesticides.
- The contents of lead and cadmium may be determined by inverse voltammetry or by atomic emission spectrophotometry.
- The following maximum amounts in dried plant materials, which are based on the ADI values, are proposed.
- lead,10mg/kg, cadmium,0.3 mg/kg.

(g) Determination of microorganisms

Usually, medicinal plants containing bacteria and molds are coming from soil and atmosphere. Analysis of the limits of E. coli and molds clearly throws light on the harvesting and production practices. The substance known as aflatoxins will produce serious side effects if consumed along with the crude drugs. The following table shows the maximum limits of microorganisms allowed in raw materials and finished products.

Table 1 Limits of microorganisms allowed in raw materials and finished products.

Microorganisms	Raw material	Finished products
E Coli	10 ⁶	10 ¹
Salmonella	NIL	NIL
Total aerobic bacteria	10 ⁵	NIL
Enterobacteria	10 ³	NIL

(h)Alfa toxin content

- Aflatoxins are naturally occurring mycotoxins produced mainly by Aspergillus flavus and Aspergillus parasiticus.
- The presence of aflatoxins can be determined by chromatographic methods using standard aflatoxins B1, B2, G1, G2 mixtures,

➤ IP method: NMT 2 µg/kg of aflatoxins B1& Total aflatoxins 4 µg/kg.

➤ USP method: NMT 5ppb of aflatoxins B1& Total aflatoxins 20ppb.

(i)Radioactive contamination

- Microbial growth in herbals is usually avoided by irradiation. This process may sterilize the plant material but the

radioactivity hazard should be taken into account.

- The range of radionuclides that may be released into the environment as a result of nuclear accidents might include long-lived and short-lived fission products, actinides, and activation products.
- The nature and the intensity of radionuclides released may differ markedly and depend on the source (reactor, reprocessing plant, fuel fabrication plant, isotope production unit, etc).
- The radioactivity of the plant samples should be checked according to the guidelines of International Atomic Energy (IAE) in Vienna and that of WHO.

3.8. STABILITY TESTING OF HERBAL DRUGS

- Herbal drugs may be a single active constituent or entire herb or a combination of herbs consisting of a mixture of constituents. Most of the herbal drug products used are a group of constituents. Stability testing of herbal products is a complicated issue because the entire herb or herbal product is regarded as the active substance, regardless of whether constituents with defined therapeutic activity are known.
- The stability testing of herbal products includes checking the quality which varies with me under the influence of environmental factors, such as temperature, humidity, light, oxygen, moisture, other ingredients or excipients in the dosage form, particle size of drug, microbial contamination, trace metal contamination, leaching from the container, etc. and also provides statistics for the determination of shelf life.
- Therefore, evaluation of the parameters based on chemical, physical, microbiological, therapeutic, and toxicological studies can serve as an important tool in stability studies.

4. PROBLEMS RELATED TO THE HERBAL, PRODUCT STABILITY

Physical instability

Natural medicines are usually prone to physical instability due to the presence of impurities and reactions with the container. Conditions like the growth of the microorganisms feeding affect the secondary metabolites and chemical composition of plants Volatile active components of natural medicine have the problem of volatility and decreasing activity during storage for a long time.

Environmental conditions

Environmental conditions such as rainfall, altitude, temperature, soil, storage conditions well as different harvesting procedures, time and method of collection, manufacturing processes such as selecting, drying, purifying, extracting, and genetic variability can create substantial variability in the product quality, stability and in the concentration of plant constituents. Light is also an important factor affecting Phyto- medicines by generating free radicals.

Chemical instability

Herbal drugs are subjected to degradation during storage by oxidation, hydrolysis crystallization, emulsion breakdown, enzymatic deterioration, and chemical reactions with additives and excipients. Temperature and moisture are the two major factors that affect the quality and stability of an herbal product. A chemical reaction increases by two to three for every 10°C rise in temperature. Moisture absorbed onto the surface of a solid drug often increases the rate of decomposition if it is susceptible to hydrolysis. The presence of enzymes in the product also increases the rate of chemical degradation.

Complex mixtures, variability, and inconsistency

Herbal formulations are complex mixtures of different components obtained during the extraction process. Each component has variable shelf-life, activity, concentration, and consistency. It creates a problem during storage condition determination as it is not easy to determine the stability of the final herbal preparation based on the activity and stability profile of a single component.

Drug interactions, deterioration, decomposition, and storage

Moisture content above the critical value and mold growth in natural products can cause the interaction of the active components with the packaging material, and interactions of active components with the other ingredients of formulations used such as additives cause alteration in the novel drug activity. Herbal formulations have many active constituents such as alkaloids, glycosides, tannins, flavonoids, etc. Each component has different stability conditions. Hence actual stability condition for the herbal formulation is different than its individual components.

Stability studies should be performed on at least three production batches of the herbal product for the proposed shelf life, which is normally denoted as long-term stability and is performed under natural atmospheric conditions. With the help of modern analytical techniques like spectrophotometry, HPLC,

HPTLC and by employing proper guidelines it is possible to generate a sound stability data of herbal

products and predict their shelf-life, which will help in improving global acceptability of herbal products.

5. REGULATIONS:

Table 2: Regulation Authorities in India

Parameters	Authorities	India
Herbal Medicines	Legislation	The Drugs and Cosmetics Act 1940 amended 1964. The Bureau of Indian Standards Act 1986
	Committee	Department of AYUSH
	Responsible Regulatory authorities for Registration of Nutraceuticals	Food Safety and Standards Authority of India (FSSAI)
Neutraceuticals	Form & Regulatory Requirements for Registration	Form A, B & C A. Product evaluation B. Licenses C. Health & label claim
	Authority	Central Drugs Standard Control Organisation (CDSCO)
	Rules & Regulation	D&C Act ,1940 AND Rules1945
Herbal Cosmetics	Pre-Marketing Approval	Requirements under the state government
	Post Marketing Reporting System	N/A
Phytopharmaceuticals	Authority	Central Drug Standard Control Organization (CDSCO)

6. Guidelines of Herbals approval for formulation in India:

India controls herbal goods under a number of systems, including Ayurveda, Unani, Siddha, and contemporary medicine as was previously indicated. The Ministry of AYUSH and the Central Drugs Standard Control Organization (CDSCO) are among the regulatory bodies.

Approval process of Herbals in India:

Ayurveda, Yoga, Unani, Naturopathy, Siddha, and Homeopathy are the known health systems in India, along with Homeopathy, and all of them rely heavily

on herbal medicine not on Allopathic medicine. Herbal medicine is governed in India by the Central Council of Indian Medicine Act, Research Councils, Department of AYUSH, and D&C Act 1940(Amendment). Together, the AYUSH department, the Indian Council of Medical Research, and the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research cooperate to develop safe and effective AYUSH products for ailments that are known to exist in India as well as new Pharmaceuticals. Drug and Cosmetic Act of 1940 and its Rules of 1945(D&C ACT) apply to herbal medications. As a general rule, Ayurvedic, Unani, or Siddha drugs include all medications produced entirely in accordance with the formulae

described in the valid books of Siddha, the system of Ayurvedic and Unani medicine, which are listed in the very first schedule. These medications may be used internally or externally, or in the diagnosis of disease, treatment of disease, mitigation of disease, or curing of disease or disorder in humans or animals. The

license, formulation composition manufacture, labeling, packing, quality, and export control are all expanded under the D&C Act contains Good Manufacturing Practice (GMP) regulations that apply to the production of herbal medications.

Table:3. Approval process of Herbals in India

Parts of Act/Rule	Chapter/Part	Nature of Activity
Drugs and Cosmetics Act 1940	Chapter IV-A (section 33-B to 33-N)	Provides provisions related to Ayurveda, Siddha and Unani Drugs
	The first schedule	List of scheduled books
	The second schedule	Standards to be complied with by imported drugs and by drugs manufactured for Sale, stocked or exhibited for Sale or Distributed
Drugs Cosmetics & Rules 1945	Part XVI (Rule 151-160)	Manufacture for sale of Ayurvedic (including Siddha) or Unani Drugs
	Part XVI-A (Rule 160A-160J)	Approval of institutions for carrying out tests on ASU Drugs and Raw material used in their manufacture
	Part XVII (Rule 161)	Labelling, Packing and Limit of Alcohol in ASU Drugs
	Part XVII (Rule 161-B)	Shelf life and date of expiry for ASU Medicines
	Part XVIII (Rule 162-167)	Government analysts and Inspectors for ASU Drugs
	Part XIX (Rule 168-170)	Standard of ASU Drugs
Drugs Cosmetics & Rules 1945- Schedules	Schedule A	Different types of forms, particularly 24D,24E,25D,25E,26D,26E,26E-1,47,48,49
	Schedule B-1	Fees for the test or analysis by pharmacopeial Laboratory for Indian Medicine or the Govt. Analyst
	Schedule E-1	List of poisonous substances under ASU Systems of Medicine
	Schedule FF	Standards for Ophthalmic Preparation
	Schedule T	Good Manufacturing Practices for ASU Medicine
	Schedule Y	Requirements and guidelines for permission to import and /or manufacture new drug sales and undertake clinical trials
	(Prospected) Schedule Z	Requirements and guidelines for permission to manufacture ASU Drugs for sale and clinical trials.

6.1. List of Documents Required for Application for WHO-GMP for ASU -Herbal Drugs [9,11]

1. Application for WHO-GMP certification & issuance of COPP.
2. Name of the applicant with address, telephone, fax, e-mail, etc.
3. Copy of Manufacturing license.
4. List of approved products.
5. List of products for which the firm has valid COPP.
6. List of products applied for issuance of COPP & their composition.
7. Site Master file (as specified under WHO TRS 823).
8. Data on Finished formulation:

- 8.01: master manufacturing formula, manufacturing process.
- 8.02: finished product specification and method of analysis
- 8.03: stability study evaluation (accelerated and real-time) for 3 batches including details batch size, Batch No., Date of manufacturing, Date of Expiry, stability study condition (Accelerated/ Real-time), Name of Drug, etc. (as per Format-A)
- 8.04 Process validation report for 3 batches.
- 8.05 Validation report of analytical method,
9. List of technical staff, their qualification, experience, and approval status.

10. List of equipment and instruments.
11. List of SOPs and STPs.
12. Manufacturing Plant layout.
13. Schematic diagram of water system specifying circulation loop and MOC.
14. Schematic diagram of HVAC system specifying terminal filter configuration.
15. Export data of the last 2 years, in case of re-validation of COPP.
- 16 Product summary sheet (as per Format B).
17. Actual labels of the products applied for WHO-COPP.
18. Proof of safety and effectiveness as per Rule 158B of Drugs & Cosmetic Rules, 1945.
19. Reference standards of the ingredients/formulation of the products applied for WHO-COPP.
20. Certificates of Analysis for three batches of each product.
21. Undertaking regarding the absence of any non-herbal ingredients including metals/ minerals, etc. in the products applied for WHO-COPPs.
22. Undertaking regarding compliance to the provisions of domestic regulations inter alia. Drugs and Cosmetics Act, 1940 and Rules thereunder, Drugs and Magic Remedies (Objectionable Advertisements) Act, 1954 and Rules thereunder, etc.

7. Ministry of AYUSH [8]

On November 9, 2014, the Ministry of AYUSH was established to oversee the successful advancement and dissemination of AYUSH healthcare systems. The Department of Naturopathy and Yoga, Ayurvedic, Siddha, Unani, and Homeopathy (AYUSH), which was established in March 1995 and formerly known as the Department of Indian System of Medicine and Homeopathy (ISM&H), centered its efforts on the advancement of education and research in these fields.

a. The Goals of AYUSH

- The primary goal is to raise the bar for education at the nation's colleges and universities teaching the Indian System of Medicine and homeopathy.
- To strengthen the already-existing research institutes and ensure that a one-time research program on recognizable disorders results in an effective cure for these systems.
- To develop a plan for the propagation, cultivation, and regrowth of medicinal plants used in the aforementioned systems.

- To provide pharmacopeial criteria for medications used in homeopathy and the Indian System of Medicine.
- To regulate the quality of medications by establishing pharmacopeial standards, supervising the operations of the pharmacopeial laboratory for Indian medicines under the auspices of the Quality Council of India, and keeping an eye on the actions of the Indian Medicine Pharmaceutical Company Limited.
- AYUSH also supervises the implementation of GMPs, the construction of shared facilities in accordance with the cluster approach, and the execution of the Drug Quality Control scheme with the disclosure of herbal medical formulations, knowledge & manuscripts, documentation, and promotion of local medical customs.
- The Quality Council of India and the AYUSH department set up a certification program for AYUSH pharmaceutical items. Regarding the standards of AYUSH products in terms of their quality, safety, and efficacy, people have always been worried.
- To allay these worries, the Quality Council of India has launched a new voluntary certification program for AYUSH products.

b. Attestation by AYUSH [11]

Two levels of AYUSH certification are offered:

- a) Based on conformity with domestic regulatory requirements, the AYUSH Standard Mark.
- b) AYUSH Premium Mark, determined by the following possibilities:

Option A: Complying with GMP requirements in accordance with WHO guidelines and the contamination limits specified in the certification criteria.

Option B: Adherence to import nation regulations as long as they are tougher than option A above.

8. Challenges Associated

Herbal medicines are introduced into the market without any mandatory safety or toxicological evaluation regarding the effect of the drug. Many of these countries also lack effective machinery to regulate manufacturing practices and quality standards of the herbal medicine. Challenges often encountered and common to many countries are those related to regulatory status, assessment of safety and efficacy, quality control, safety monitoring, and inadequate or poor knowledge about traditional, complementary/alternatives.

a. Challenges Associated with The Regulatory Status of Herbal Medicines

According to the definitions dietary supplement is a product that is ingested and is intended to supplement the diet and contains a “dietary ingredient”. The dietary ingredients in these products may include different vitamins, minerals, herbs, or other botanicals required by the body.

Under the DSHEA, any additional toxicity studies are generally not required if the herb has been on the market before 1994. For this, the FDA hauls the burden to prove that an herbal medicinal product or “dietary ingredient” is toxic or not safe for use. The additional major challenge in many countries is related to the fact that regulatory information on herbal medicines is often not shared between regulatory authorities and safety monitoring or pharmacovigilance centers.

b. Challenges Associated with the Assessment of Safety and Efficacy

No one can contradict the fact that the requirements as well as the research protocols, standards, and methods needed for the evaluation of the safety and efficacy of herbal medicines are much more complex than those required for conventional or orthodox pharmaceuticals. A single herbal medicine or medicinal plant may contain more than hundreds of natural constituents, and a mixed herbal medicinal product may contain several times the number of one. Such an analysis of single active constituents may practically be impossible especially where an herbal product is in a mixture of two or more herbs.

c. Challenges Associated with Quality Control of Herbal Medicine

The quality of the raw materials used in the production of herbal medicines determines to a large extent the safety and efficacy. The quality source or raw materials is dependent not only on intrinsic (genetic) factors but also on extrinsic factors such as environmental conditions, good agriculture, and good collection practices for medicinal plants, including plant selection and cultivation. It is the combination of many factors that make it difficult to perform quality controls on the raw materials of herbal medicines.

According to good manufacturing practice (GMP), correct identification of species of medicinal plants, special storage, and special cleaning methods for various materials are important requirements for quality control of starting materials. The major challenges are in the quality control of finished herbal medicinal products, especially a mixture of herbal products. Hence, the general requirements and methods for

quality control of finished herbal products remain much more complex than for other pharmaceuticals. To ensure the safety and efficacy of herbal medicines, the WHO continues to ensure the institution of quality assurance and control measures such as National Quality Specification and standards for herbal materials, GMP, labeling, and licensing schemes for manufacturing.

d. Challenges Associated to the Safety Monitoring of Herbal Medicines

In the past few years, issues relating to the increasing use of herbal or natural medicines or products in developed countries. Furthermore, the dependence of many people living in developing countries on plants as a major source of medicines coupled with weak regulation of herbal medicines in most countries and the occurrence of high-profile safety concerns has increased awareness regarding the need to monitor safety and understanding of possible harmful as well as potential benefits linked with the use of herbal medicines. Adverse effects arising from the consumption of herbal medicines is due to several factors among which include the use of the wrong species of plant, adulteration of herbal products, undeclared medicines, contamination, overdosage, misuse of herbal medicines by either health-care providers or consumers, and use of herbal medicines with other medicines. There is a lack of proper knowledge regarding the importance of taxonomic botany and documentation by most manufacturers of herbal medicines, and this poses peculiar challenges during the identification and collection of medicinal plants used for herbal remedies. To overcome the confusion created because of the common names, it is necessary to adopt the most commonly used binomial names for medicinal plants. For example, *Artemisia absinthium*, which has at least 11 common names, and contains an active narcotic derivative. Hence, the effective monitoring of herbal medicine will require effective collaboration between botanists, Phytochemists, pharmacologists, and other major stakeholders.

9. Future Prospects

The future is in the phase of increasing demand and the fast-growing market of herbal medicines and other herbal healthcare products, in both developing and developed countries of the world. Here are some areas where herbal products are expected to make an impact.

- ❖ Increased mainstream acceptance: Herbal products are becoming more widely accepted in mainstream healthcare, leading to increased adoption and integration with conventional medicine.

- ❖ Personalized medicine: Herbal products may play a crucial role in personalized medicine, as they can be tailored to individual needs and health profiles.
- ❖ Preventive healthcare: Herbal products are well-suited for preventive healthcare, promoting overall wellness and disease prevention.
- ❖ Sustainable and eco-friendly: Herbal products are often seen as a more sustainable and eco-friendly option, aligning with the growing demand for natural and organic products.
- ❖ Innovative formulations: Advances in technology and research will lead to innovative herbal formulations, such as nano-emulsions and liposomes, enhancing bioavailability and efficacy.
- ❖ Global market growth: The global herbal market is expected to grow significantly, driven by increasing demand in emerging markets and expanding distribution channels.
- ❖ Regulatory framework development: As the industry grows, regulatory frameworks will evolve to ensure quality, safety, and efficacy standards for herbal products.
- ❖ Research and development: Ongoing research will uncover new herbal ingredients, extraction methods, and applications, driving innovation and growth.
- ❖ Digital health integration: Herbal products may be incorporated into digital health platforms, enabling personalized recommendations and monitoring.
- ❖ Collaboration and partnerships: The herbal industry will see increased collaboration between researchers, manufacturers, and healthcare professionals, driving progress and innovation.

10. CONCLUSION:

Herbal medicine makes a tiny contribution to modern healthcare, which has a market worth billions of dollars. This is due to a lack of knowledge, technical and regulatory challenges, a lack of motivation pharmaceutical companies, and the industry's little market engagement.

The demand for Herbal products is growing daily thus both developed and emerging nations are more concerned about their use and safety. One of the biggest issues the herbal market is dealing with is a lack of harmonization. Strict actions must be conducted to harmonize global regulatory requirements to maintain vigilance. To achieve this,

global harmonization of legislation is needed to guide the responsible production and marketing of herbal medicines. If sufficient scientific evidence of benefit is available for an herb, then such legislation should allow for this to be used appropriately to promote the use of that herb so that these benefits can be realized for the promotion of public health and the treatment of diseases.

Therefore, regulatory policies on herbal medicines need to be standardized and strengthened on a global scale. It is now on the shoulders of the regulatory bodies to monitor the controlled and quality flow of herbal products and to facilitate their development in clinical trial stages.

11. REFERENCES:

1. Akash Jyoti, Prasad D.N, Shahnaz Mohammad, Dev Dhruv. Herbs As Traditional Medicines: A Review. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics*.2018;8(5):146-150.
2. Gavali Pratiksha Suresh, Garute Komal Somnath, Prof. Sidhir Garje sir, ghavale aarti Sanjay. Advance Herbal Technology. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts*.2022.10(1) January 2022.ISSN:2320-288. <https://ijcrt.org/papers/IJCRT2201416.pdf>.
3. Neha Singh, Meenakshi Gqarg and Rajini Chopra. An Overview of Formulation: From Processing to Pharmacovigilance. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Science and Research* 2023;14(2) <https://ijpsr.com/bft-article/an-overview-of-herbal-formulations-from-processing-to-pharmacovigilance/>
4. Jiwan P Jiwan P. Lavande, Sanjay K. Bais, Avinash Siddharam Gurav. Review on Quality aspects of herbal drugs and it's formulations. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Applications*.2023; 8 (1). https://ijprajournal.com/issue_dcp/Review%20on%20Quality%20aspects%20of%20herbal%20drugs%20and%20its%20formulations.
5. Thillaivanan. S, Samraj. K. Challenges, constraints and opportunities in Herbs Medicines-A Review. *International Journal of Herbal Medicines*.2014;2(1);21-24. <https://www.florajournal.com/vol2issue1/april2014/4>.
6. Junhua Zhang, Igho J. Onakpoya, Paul Posadzki and Mohamed Eddouks. The Safety of Herbal Medicine: from Prejudice to Evidence. *Pub Med Central*.2015. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC4370194/>
7. Shubbham Bhardwaj, Rajeswari Verma, Jyoti Gupta. Challenges and future aspects of herbal

- medicine. International Research in Medical and Health sciences. 2018; 1(1). <https://irmhs.com/index.php/irmhs/article/view/26/>
8. Ministry of Ayush[Internet].India:AYUSH;2023 Oct 04. Available from: <https://www.ayush.gov.in/>.
 9. CDSCO, List of documents required for application for WHO-GMP/CoPp for A.S.U. herbal drugs, May 31 2018.
 10. Ministry of Ayush [Internet]. India: AYUSH; 2021 Apr 14 [cited 2023 June 18]. Available from: <https://www.ayush.gov.in/>.
 11. Voluntary certification scheme for Ayush products [Internet]. India: Indian Register Quality Systems (IRQS);2021 [cited 2023 Sep. 02]. <https://www.irqs.co.in/voluntary-certification-scheme-forayush-products/>
 12. Sharma S. Current status of herbal product: regulatory overview. Journal of Pharmacy and Bioallied Sciences. 2015; 7(4):293-6. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC4678984/>
 13. Anupama S, Vikas AS, Vandana K, Anil B. Current status of regulations for herbal medicine in Europe, USA and India. International Journal of Natural Sciences Research. 2011,2(3):406-22.
 14. Nitin V. Herbal medicines: regulation and practice in Europe, United States and India. International journal of Herbal Medicines .2013;1(4):1-5.
 15. Ganesh G, Ramachandran A, Suresh KR, Senthil V, Baviya PR. Nutraceuticals - A regulatory review. International Journal of Drug Regulatory Affairs. 2015;3(2):22-9. <https://www.ijdra.com/index.php/journal/article/view/165>